

Key Areas of Cattle Care and Management by Dairy Producers:

We appreciate your time and help on this project! Your participation in this study is voluntary and anonymous. Your responses will assist in the improvement of cattle care and management within your communities.

If you prefer a mobile-friendly format, use the QR code to quickly answer the questions on your device. Or mail this survey in the postage-paid envelope.

If you would like to participate in future projects related to cattle care, please provide the best contact info at the end of this survey.

1. Are you currently dairy farming?
 - Yes
 - No
2. Are dairy cows calving on your farm?
 - Yes
 - No
3. How many years of dairy farming experience do you have? **Select one.**
 - 0-2 years
 - 3-5 years
 - 5-7 years
 - 7-9 years
 - 10 or more years
4. Please select the option that best describes your role on the farm. **Select one.**
 - Farm Owner
 - Manager
 - Family member of owner
 - Employee - Non-family of owners
 - Other (specify)
5. Please indicate your age category. **Select one.**
 - < 20 years
 - 20 to 29 years
 - 30 to 39 years
 - 40 to 49 years
 - 50 to 59 years
 - 60 to 69 years
 - > 70 years
6. Which of the following best describes your HIGHEST level of formal education? **Select one.**
 - Some high school
 - Completed high school
 - Completed apprenticeship training or trade school
 - Some college or university
 - Completed bachelor's degree at a college or university
 - Completed a graduate degree (e.g. Masters degree)
 - Professional degree

HOW MUCH LIKE YOU IS THIS PERSON?

Here we briefly describe some people. Please read each description and think about how much each person is or is not like you. Using a 6-point scale from “not like me at all” to “very much like me,” choose how similar the person is to you.

6	5	4	3	2	1
Very much like me	Like me	Somewhat like me	A little like me	Not like me	Not like me at all

- _____ 1. They believe they should always show respect to those with authority and to older people. It is important for them to be obedient.
- _____ 2. Religious belief is important to them. They try hard to do what their religion requires.
- _____ 3. It is very important to them to help the people around them. They want to care for their well-being.
- _____ 4. They think it is important that every person in the world be treated equally. They believe everyone should have equal opportunities in life.
- _____ 5. They think it is important to be interested in things. They like to be curious and to try to understand all sorts of things.
- _____ 6. They like to take risks. They are always looking for adventures.
- _____ 7. They take every chance they can to have fun. It is important to them to do things that give them pleasure.
- _____ 8. Getting ahead in life is important to them. They strive to do better than others.
- _____ 9. They always want to be the one who makes the decisions. They like to be the leader.
- _____ 10. It is important to them that things be organized and clean. They really do not like things to be a mess.
- _____ 11. It is important to them to always behave properly. They want to avoid doing anything people would say is wrong.
- _____ 12. They think it is best to do things in traditional ways. It is important to them to keep up the customs they have learned.
- _____ 13. It is important to them to respond to the needs of others. They try to support those they know.
- _____ 14. They believe all the worlds' people should live in harmony. Promoting peace among all groups in the world is important to them.
- _____ 15. Thinking up new ideas and being creative is important to them. They like to do things in their own original way.
- _____ 16. They think it is important to do lots of different things in life. They always look for new things to try.
- _____ 17. They really want to enjoy life. Having a good time is very important to them.
- _____ 18. Being very successful is important to them. They like to impress other people.
- _____ 19. It is important to them to be in charge and tell others what to do. They want people to do what they say.
- _____ 20. Having a stable government is important to them. They are concerned with the social order being protected.

7. How many cows are you MILKING in your herd today?

8. Which breed is the majority of your milking herd?

- Holstein
- Jersey
- Other (specify)_____

9. Please choose the type of barn in which you house most (>50%) of the MILKING cows in your herd. **Select one.**

- Free stall barn
- Tie stall barn
- Bedded pack
- Other (specify)_____

10. What best describes the type of milking system you use to milk the majority (>50%) of your herd? **Select one.**

- Pipe-line
- Parlour
- Robotic milking system
- Other (specify)_____

11. Do you produce organically certified milk on your operation?

- Yes
- No

12. Indicate the frequency of regularly scheduled visits with the herd veterinarian (e.g. Herd Health)? **Select one.**

- Weekly
- Every 2 weeks
- Monthly
- Every 2 months
- More than every 2 months
- The farm does not have regularly scheduled visits with a veterinarian

Please answer the following questions as they pertain to calf management

13. Do you typically feed colostrum to your **female** calves?

- Yes
- No -----> **Skip to Question 17**

14. What percentage of your **female** calves receive the following types of colostrum? (*The following should add up to 100%*)

% of Calves	Colostrum Type
	Raw from mother
	Raw from another herd member or a pooled colostrum
	Pasteurized colostrum from mother
	Pasteurized from another herd member or a pooled herd sample
	Dried/powdered colostrum
	Other (specify)

15. What percentage of your **female** calves are fed colostrum using the following methods? (*The following should add up to 100%*)

% of Calves	Colostrum Feeding method
	Tube
	Bottle
	Bucket
	Allow them to drink from the mother's udder (<i>if 100% skip to Q17</i>)
	Other (specify)

16. If you feed colostrum manually rather than allowing calves to nurse, how many quarts of colostrum do you offer **female** calves for their FIRST feeding?

Number of quarts _____

17. For female calves hand-fed colostrum, how many hours between birth and the first feeding of colostrum for most (>50%) of calves?

Number of hours _____

18. Do **male** calves typically receive colostrum?

- Yes
- No -----→ **Skip to Question 23**

19. What percentage of your **male** calves receive the following types of colostrum? (*The following should add up to 100%*)

Percentage of Calves	Colostrum Type
	Raw from mother
	Raw from another herd member or a pooled herd sample
	Pasteurized from mother
	Pasteurized from another herd member or a pooled herd sample
	Dried/powdered colostrum
	Other (specify)

20. What percentage of your **male** calves are fed using the following methods? (*The following should add up to 100%*)

Percentage of Calves	Colostrum Feeding method
	Tube
	Bottle
	Bucket
	Allow them to drink from the mother's udder (<i>if 100% skip to milk feeding questions</i>)
	Other (specify)

21. If you feed colostrum manually rather than allowing calves to nurse, how many quarts of colostrum do you offer **male** calves for their first feeding?

Number of quarts _____

22. For **male** calves hand-fed colostrum, how many hours between birth and the first feeding of colostrum for most (>50%) of calves?

Number of hours _____

23. Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements

Question	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
My male calves are receiving optimal care					
I cannot provide the level of care I wish to provide to male calves due to the financial cost					
I would rather my male calves go to a dairy-beef grower than a veal grower.					
Euthanizing male calves on-farm is a reasonable alternative when their selling price is very low					
A price premium would influence my decision to give male calves more or higher quality colostrum					
If I received a consistent, baseline price for my male calves I would provide a higher level of care					
A price discount for male calves in poor condition would motivate me to provide a higher level of care					
Male calves are a valuable part of the dairy industry					
As a farmer, it is my job to provide optimal care to male dairy calves while they are on the farm					
I cannot provide the level of care I wish to provide to male calves because of the workload of the rest of the dairy herd					

24. At what age do you sell the majority (>50%) of your male calves? **Select one.**

- Within 3 days
- 3 to 7 days
- 8 to 10 days
- 11 to 14 days
- After 14 days but before weaning
- After weaning
- I keep my male calves to raise for veal or beef

25. What percentage (%) of your male calves are marketed in the following ways? (*total should add to 100%*)

% of calves	Marketing Method
	Euthanized on-farm at birth
	Calves are taken to an auction
	Calves are taken directly to another farm where they are raised for veal or beef
	Calves are taken directly to a slaughter facility
	Calves are picked up, but I do not know where they go
	Other (specify)

26. Does someone from your farm typically deliver the male calves to their destination (e.g. auction)?

- Yes, someone from my farm has to deliver the calves
- No, someone else outside the farm picks up the calves.

27. What percent of your dairy animals are bred with beef sires/semen in order to improve profitability of male calves (not because of fertility problems in the cow)? **Select one.**

- 0%
- 1-25%
- 26-50%
- 51-75%
- 76-100%

28. How often does the person buying your male calves give you any feedback (positive or negative) on their health or productivity at their final destination (eg. slaughter facility, calf rearing facility)?

- Never -----→ **Skip to 30**
- Sometimes
- Always

29. Have you ever changed any of your male calf care practices based on the information you received from the buyer?

- Yes
- No

30. When deciding what calf care practices to use, how important do you consider the opinions of the following dairy industry stakeholders?

Stake holder	Not important	Of little importance	Moderately important	Important	Very Important
Other dairy farmers	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Calf buyers	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Veal producers	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Dairy beef producers	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Public	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Milk processor	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Your herd veterinarian	<input type="checkbox"/>				

31. Does your farm have employees (non-family labor) who provide care for the calves?
 Yes
 No

Please answer the following questions as they pertain to treatment practices

32. Are you involved or have you been involved with the treatment of sick adult dairy cows on the farm (including writing protocols)?
 Yes
 No

33. The following question asks about the availability of a standardized protocol for treating sick cows. **Please answer all 3 questions for the three diseases listed.**

	Does your farm have a treatment protocol?			Was the protocol written or approved by a veterinarian?			Does the protocol include how to identify sick cows?		
	Yes	No	I don't know	Yes	No	I don't know	Yes	No	I don't know
Metritis									
Mastitis									
Lameness									

34. Thinking of the last 10 times you treated an animal with antibiotics on your farm, for how many of the times was the use consistent with what was written in a protocol?
 None
 1 to 3
 4 to 6
 7 to 9
 All 10

35. Once you have made the decision to treat with an antibiotic, what are the most important reasons for you to select a particular antibiotic product? Use the numbers 1 through 5 to rank them in order from the most important to less important”.

- _____ My own experience with similar cases
- _____ Recommendations from my veterinarian
- _____ Other producers’ advice
- _____ My farm’s written protocol for the disease
- _____ Price of the product
- _____ The length of the withholding period
- _____ Ease of administration
- _____ Having an on-label indication for the condition I am treating
- _____ Potential development of antibiotic resistance
- _____ Other (specify)

36. Do you give cows intramammary antibiotics at dry-off (dry cow therapy)? **Select one.**

- Yes, we use dry-cow therapy for all cows
- We only use dry-cow therapy for some of the cows (selective dry cow therapy)
- None of the cows get dry-cow therapy.

37. Imagine the following scenario. You observe a fresh cow 14 days in milk in her 2nd lactation with odorless, reddish-brown vaginal discharge. The cow gets up normally and is active and eating well. The cow’s rectal temperature is 102.0°F. Select all the immediate actions you would normally take. **Select all that apply.**

- Give an anti-inflammatory drug (e.g. Banamine, flunixin)
- Fluid therapy (e.g., oral drench)
- An injection of hormones (e.g. Lutalyse, PGF2, prostaglandin)
- Intrauterine infusion of disinfectants (e.g., iodine)
- Intrauterine infusion of antibiotics
- Injection of antibiotics
- Delay treatment until the veterinarian comes
- No immediate treatment is necessary—continue to observe the cow
- Other _____

38. You observe a fresh cow 14 days in milk in her 2nd lactation with a reddish-brown vaginal discharge with a foul-smelling odor. The cow shows signs of weakness and is slow to get up. Her rectal temperature is 103.5°F. **Select all that apply.**

- Give an anti-inflammatory drug (e.g. Banamine, flunixin)
- Fluid therapy (e.g., oral drench)
- An injection of hormones (e.g. Lutalyse, PGF2, prostaglandin)
- Intrauterine infusion of disinfectants (e.g., iodine)
- Intrauterine infusion of antibiotics
- Injection of antibiotics
- Delay treatment until the veterinarian comes
- No immediate treatment is necessary—continue to observe the cow
- Other _____

39. You observe a fresh cow 14 DIM in her 2nd lactation with a reddish-brown vaginal discharge with a foul-smelling odor. The cow shows no apparent signs of weakness when she gets up, and is active and eating well when you observed her. The cow's rectal temperature is 102.0°F. **Select all that apply.**

- Give an anti-inflammatory drug (e.g. Banamine, flunixin)
- Fluid therapy (e.g., oral drench)
- An injection of hormones (e.g. Lutalyse, PGF2, prostaglandin)
- Intrauterine infusion of disinfectants (e.g., iodine)
- Intrauterine infusion of antibiotics
- Injection of antibiotics
- Delay treatment until the veterinarian comes
- No immediate treatment is necessary—continue to observe the cow
- Other _____

40. What proportion of all the antibiotic treatments on your farm are recorded (either in your computer or in a logbook)? **Select one.**

- 0 to 25%
- 26 to 50%
- 51 to 75%
- 76 to 98%
- 99-100%

41. From the following, indicate your level of agreement for the following statements.

Question	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
I only record treatments that have a milk withdrawal					
I only record treatments in lactating cows					
I forget to write things down because I'm busy					
It's inconvenient to record treatments					
I choose not to record treatments					

42. Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements. Antibiotic resistance means that bacteria become resistant to the medications used to treat disease, so that the antibiotic medication does not work as well or does not work at all.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
There is an overuse of antibiotics in dairy production	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Selective dry cow therapy is more appropriate than blanket dry cow therapy.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I could explain what antibiotic resistance is to my neighbor	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Antibiotic resistant infections are an important problem in dairy cows (that is, antibiotics fail to work <u>in cows</u> because of resistant bacteria)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
We should reduce the use of antibiotics in dairy production	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Milk production will be reduced if antibiotic use is decreased	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
If antibiotic use is decreased, animal welfare would also decrease.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The use of antibiotics on farms could cause antibiotic resistance in <u>humans</u>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
If I knew which antibiotics are most important for human medicine, I would avoid using them in my <u>cattle</u>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
When I treat an animal, I think about the risks of antibiotic resistance in <u>cattle or humans</u>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I have had a discussion with my veterinarian about when and how to use antibiotics for treatments	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Antibiotic use in humans (prescribed by doctors) is the main cause of antibiotic resistance in humans	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Antibiotic resistant infections in people are an important problem	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
When I, as a patient, use antibiotics, I follow the prescription exactly	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

43. In your opinion, which of the following would be most effective for improved antibiotic use in the dairy industry? (select one)

- Put more regulations in place to change or reduce use of antibiotics on dairy farms.
- Provide more education or promotion to change or reduce use on dairy farms.
- Measure use and provide benchmarking to compare use among dairy farms.
- Provide incentives to change or reduce use on dairy farms.
- Don't take any action to change or reduce use on dairy farms.

44. In your view, who should take the lead on promoting responsible use of antibiotics in the dairy industry? **Select one.**

- International organizations
- The federal government
- My state government
- Milk processors
- Retailers or restaurants
- Pharmaceutical or animal health companies
- Veterinarians
- Individual farms
- No one – no changes are needed

45. Rank in order from easiest to most difficult (1 being the easiest), the group of animals you think it would be easiest to reduce antibiotic use without causing harm?

- Weaned calves and pre-breeding heifers _____
- Pre-weaned calves _____
- Breeding age and pregnant heifers _____
- Lactating cows _____
- Dry cows _____

Conclusion

If you would like to participate in future projects related to cattle care and management by dairy producers, please provide the best contact information below.

Primary phone number: _____

Email: _____

Home address: _____